

Common reasons that lead to the development of pathologies of the gastrointestinal tract

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Conclusion. *The main function of the digestive system is to perform vital functions in our body. Life is absolutely impossible without it, because thanks to its main processes (digestion of ingested nutrients and their absorption), a person receives the necessary energy for work and rest. The stomach and intestines are the main organs of digestion, and their activity is related to the initial and final stages of the entire digestive tract. If your stomach and intestines are healthy, they will never let you down. It is worth noting that the human digestive system is very sensitive. It immediately affects any, even small, changes in the internal environment of the entire body, as well as in the entire external world, which lead to various diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. They cause a lot of inconvenience to the patient: discomfort and pain.*

Keywords: *Gastritis, colitis, enteritis, gastroenteritis, flatulence.*

Introduction. Causes of gastrointestinal tract pathologies:

- a. infections that cause inflammatory processes;
- b. unhealthy diet: abuse of fatty and fried foods, fast food, dry food;
- c. smoking and alcohol abuse;
- d. sedentary lifestyle, lack of physical activity;
- e. self-administration of drugs without medical supervision;
- f. regular stress;
- g. damage to internal organs by parasites;
- h. non-observance of sanitary standards in food preparation and consumption;
- i. endocrine diseases;
- j. harmful, difficult working conditions;
- k. genetic predisposition;
- l. autoimmune diseases;
- m. congenital pathologies of the structure of internal organs.

These factors can cause various gastrointestinal diseases. Some of them can be eliminated by changing your lifestyle and following a balanced diet.

Symptoms

Symptoms often depend on the nature of the disease. However, there are common symptoms that are characteristic of a number of diseases:

- a. abdominal pain in different places;
- b. belching, nausea and vomiting;
- c. indigestion with diarrhea;

bloating and flatulence.

It is important to seek help from a therapist to determine the disease and its location. Due to vague symptoms, it is impossible to diagnose the disease independently, and self-treatment can significantly worsen the situation.

In addition to general symptoms, each disease of the gastrointestinal tract has its own symptoms.

Gastritis

It is characterized by inflammation of the mucous membrane of the stomach. The following symptoms are observed with gastritis:

- a. pain in the epigastric region (in the upper part of the abdomen);
- b. nausea and vomiting;
- c. palpitations, itching;
- d. indigestion and stool disorders;
- e. general weakness, fatigue.

Symptoms increase during acute attacks of gastritis.

Colitis

Inflammatory process of the mucous membrane of the large intestine. Symptoms are characterized by:

- a. prolonged diarrhea;
- b. painful pain in the abdomen;
- c. nausea regardless of food intake;
- d. flatulence;
- e. unpleasant taste in the mouth.

The disease is also accompanied by increased irritability, weakness and fatigue.

Cholecystitis

Inflammation of the gallbladder. Often this occurs as a result of liver damage or poor nutrition. The following symptoms are characteristic:

- a. pain in the right hypochondrium;
- b. nausea and vomiting;
- c. bitter taste in the mouth;
- d. flatulence, itching of the air.

Often, patients with cholecystitis feel weak and lose strength.

Pancreatitis

- a. Inflammation of the pancreas. The following symptoms are characteristic of this disease:
- b. pain in the left side of the abdomen;
- c. nausea, vomiting, including blood;
- d. itching and flatulence.

In the advanced stages of the disease, pancreatic dyspepsia, pancreatic dysfunction can be observed. This causes digestive problems due to lack of enzymes.

Peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum

Ulcerative lesions of the mucous membrane of the stomach and / or duodenum. Comes with symptoms:

- a. pain in the upper abdomen (under the stomach);
- b. constant or regular heartbeat;
- c. nausea and vomiting;
- d. intestinal disorders: diarrhea or constipation.

At different stages of the disease, patients experience increased weakness and fatigue.

Hepatitis

Viral liver disease. It is characterized by:

- a. Jaundice: yellowing of the mucous membranes and skin, the whites of the eyes;
- b. general weakness, fatigue;
- c. a sharp deterioration in his condition.
- d.
- e. Since liver dysfunction occurs in many cases, symptoms of indigestion and loss of appetite may appear.

Dysbacteriosis

Disturbance of intestinal microflora. It is accompanied by the following symptoms:

- a. intestinal dysfunction (diarrhea, less frequent constipation);
- b. bloating and flatulence;
- c. pain and discomfort in the intestinal area;
- d. nausea, palpitations, itching;
- e. bad breath;
- f. decreased appetite.

The disease is often accompanied by an allergic reaction in the form of rashes and itching on the surface of the skin.

Diagnosis of gastrointestinal diseases

The therapist in our clinic in Kaluga makes a complete diagnosis, which includes:

1. collecting anamnesis and symptoms from the patient's words;
2. examination using palpation, percussion, auscultation;
3. instrumental examination: ultrasound;
4. laboratory studies.

Depending on the nature and location of the disease, appropriate instrumental studies are selected. It is important to assess the condition of internal organs and the degree of disease. Endoscopic diagnostic methods are necessary in cases where visual assessment of the condition of the mucous membrane of the esophagus, stomach and intestines is important.

Treatment of gastrointestinal diseases in Kaluga

Individual treatment of each disease includes elimination of symptoms, pathological processes and restoration of organ function. For this purpose, the following can be defined:

Drug treatment. Medicines are carefully selected according to the picture of the disease.

Physiotherapy treatment. Procedures designed to stimulate the activity of internal organs.

Correction of nutrition. Depending on the pathology, a diet is prescribed, excluding fatty foods and certain foods.

Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract can be diagnosed and treated both in the acute stage and during the period of silence. Therefore, if you regularly suffer from abdominal pain and discomfort, make an appointment with a therapist. Our doctor will conduct a complete examination and prescribe the appropriate treatment for you.

Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract are usually associated with problems in the functioning of other systems of the human body. They are accompanied by unpleasant, painful symptoms and require urgent treatment.

Everyone always wants to be healthy, full of energy and enjoy all the pleasures of life. However, unfortunately, recently there has been a trend of development of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract all over the world.

Gastrointestinal diseases According to scientists, the reason for this is poor nutrition, regular stress, environmental problems and many harmful substances that surround us all the time.

The main function of the digestive system is to perform vital functions in our body. Life is absolutely impossible without it, because thanks to its main processes (digestion of ingested nutrients and their absorption), a person receives the necessary energy for work and rest. The stomach and intestines are the main organs of digestion, and their activity is related to the initial and final stages of the entire digestive tract. If your stomach and intestines are healthy, they will never let you down.

It is worth noting that the human digestive system is very sensitive. It immediately affects any, even small, changes in the internal environment of the entire body, as well as in the entire external world, which lead to various diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. They cause a lot of inconvenience to the patient: discomfort and pain.

What is the gastrointestinal tract (GIT)?

To understand the principle of the gastrointestinal tract, you must first understand what it actually is. The gastrointestinal tract is a system of organs whose purpose is to process and extract all the nutrients needed by the body from food, to help the absorption of the resulting nutrients into the blood, and also to completely remove them from the body. is to remove leftover food. digested.

What is the gastrointestinal tract? The entire gastrointestinal tract in the body is represented by a continuous tube that connects the oral cavity with the anal opening. Food masses move along it in the caudal direction, they are divided into smaller particles suitable for absorption in the process of movement.

For example, the average length of the gastrointestinal tract in an adult man reaches 6.5 meters.

Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract are a group of diseases that affect this anatomical region. All pathologies are divided into several main groups, including:

by nature of development, infectious and non-infectious;

according to the location of the disease: small intestine, large intestine, stomach or esophagus;

acquired and hereditary diseases.

Causes of gastrointestinal diseases

The main reasons for the development of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract are: improper nutrition or its complete absence, strict diet or overeating, various stressful situations, infections, sedentary lifestyle, etc.

Causes of gastrointestinal diseases For example, Tibetan medicine considers the human body as a whole, interconnected and absolutely indivisible thing. Here we highlight another reason for problems with the gastrointestinal tract, that is, problems in the functioning of other systems of the human body. For example, the health of the spine is reflected in the functioning of all digestive organs.

Absolutely all internal organs are innervated by nerves coming out of the spinal canal. Any organ can function fully only if nerve impulses flow to it without hindrance. A disease such as osteochondrosis pinches the nerve endings, thereby slowing down and even preventing the normal transmission of impulses.

Because of this, the stomach relaxes and the smooth muscles of its walls relax. In case of long-term disruption of the innervation, the stomach descends. In addition, weak and weak muscles of the gastrointestinal tract are one of the reasons for poor digestion of food.

In turn, poorly digested food is not able to fully nourish the body and thus disrupts the functioning of other important body systems. Incorrect functioning of the gastrointestinal tract is also manifested in the form of decreased immunity, skin damage and metabolic diseases.

The main symptoms of diseases of the digestive system:

1. symptoms of diseases of the digestive system, pain in the abdominal cavity, different localization and different intensity;
2. Belching and heartburn;
3. Nausea and vomiting;
4. Stool disorder;
5. Flatulence and rumbling in the stomach;
6. white coating on the tongue;
7. Rapid weight loss;
8. Aversion or complete lack of appetite for some previously favorite foods.

Diagnosis of gastrointestinal diseases

Today, thanks to technological progress in modern gastroenterology, it is possible to fully diagnose all organs of the gastrointestinal tract. It consists of:

- a. Ultrasound - ultrasound examination;
- b. FGDS and irrigoscopy - endoscopy of the gastrointestinal tract;
- c. intragastric pH-metry;
- d. manometry of all digestive organs;
- e. electrogastroenterography;
- f. radiological diagnosis;
- g. biopsy.

Treatment, as well as diagnosis of any gastrointestinal diseases, is recommended to be carried out only by a qualified gastroenterologist. This will help minimize discomfort.

Prevention of digestive diseases

It is very important to prevent the occurrence and development of various problems related to the gastrointestinal tract. To do this, you must follow the following rules:

Prevention of digestive diseases Follow your diet. It is recommended to eat often and in small portions. It is very important not to skip meals, especially breakfast. Before preparing and eating each meal, wash your hands thoroughly, as well as any food that has not been heat-treated. Thus, you can protect your body from the invasion of various pathogenic microbes.

It is recommended to minimize the consumption of fried and fatty foods, as well as smoked and excessively salted foods. Instead, increase the amount of fiber: vegetables, fruits, whole grains and wholemeal bread. Eat fresh salads as much as possible, coarse fiber foods and avoid vinegar in cooking.

Don't overeat or starve yourself. In order not to feel hungry, it is recommended to eat in moderation, and then eat a meal.

Control your weight. If you have extra pounds, try to say goodbye to them. Keep in mind that rapid weight loss can also damage the gastrointestinal tract.

Minimize alcohol consumption or avoid it completely. Do not forget that low-quality alcohol contains many dyes, chemical components, as well as excess sugar, flavorings and preservatives. All this has a negative effect on the digestive system.

Stop smoking to prevent digestive diseases Quit smoking completely. Much has been said about its harm.

Avoid stressful situations. Learn to control your emotions. Walk a lot in the fresh air, rest and sleep enough. Not only will you improve your digestive system, but you will also improve your overall health.

Minimize the consumption of coffee and carbonated drinks. The recommended dose of coffee is 2-3 small cups a day, and beverages are one cup. However, it is best to avoid regular use.

Lead an active lifestyle. For adults, the norm of intensive physical activity is at least 150 minutes per week. If this indicator is not enough, it is recommended to increase it through sports.

However, if you still cannot avoid gastrointestinal tract diseases, our Diamed clinics will become your assistants in the fight against the disease. We treat the following diseases of the digestive system:

- a. different types of gastritis;
- b. gastroesophageal disease;
- c. dysbacteriosis;
- d. chronic and acute pancreatitis;
- e. litter problems;
- f. irritable bowel syndromes;
- g. colitis and flatulence;
- h. hepatosis and hepatitis;
- i. cholelithiasis;
- j. various types of hepatosis and hepatitis;
- k. peptic ulcer of the duodenum and stomach;
- l. cirrhosis.

If you need the help of a qualified gastroenterologist, you can make an appointment with specialists in our centers by calling the numbers indicated on the website or by filling out the online form.

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